

First record of the crab spider *Synema simoneae* Lessert, 1919 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The female of the crab spider *Synema simoneae* Lessert, 1919 was described from Tanzania. It is for the first time recorded from South Africa. The general morphology of the species is discussed and photographs of live specimens provided. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation are provided.

Key words: distribution, biodiversity, new record, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large areas in South Africa were surveyed (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and several *Synema* species have been collected. The genus *Synema* Simon, 1864 is presently known from 125 species and six species are so far listed from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2022).

Synema simoneae, an African endemic, was described by Lessert (1919) from Tanzania with only the female known. It is one of the species newly identified from South Africa from material sampled during SANSA surveys. It is a rare species and fewer than 25 specimens were sampled over a period of 23 years.

In the present paper, the female is redescribed and new distribution records for the species are added, as well as notes of their behaviour and conservation status.

METHODS

Material used here was obtained from the SANSA surveys and voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. Additional information was obtained from the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) and these photographs were used to provide additional information on their morphology, distribution, and behaviour.

TAXONOMY

Synema simoneae Lessert, 1919

Synema simoneae Lessert, 1919: 154 (f).

Diagnostic characteristics: Size TL: 4.1 mm. Female: carapace shiny (Fig. 1); colour varies from pale green (Fig. 2) to dark green (Fig. 7) in live specimens, eye region with fawn tint. Abdomen white, shiny, with six small black spots on border of abdomen (Figs 1–4); posteriorly with 2–3 dark transverse wavy black bands; sometimes dorsum translucent (Fig. 8). Legs I and II stronger than rest of legs; legs same colour as carapace; front legs sometimes with brownish tint. The male is still undescribed and an immature male sampled from Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve resembles the female body in shape, size, and colour of abdomen but legs I and II tibiae with red-brown bands (Fig. 3).

BEHAVIOUR

They have been sampled from vegetation by hand and sweeping the vegetation. They are occasionally found inside flower corollas. The species have been sampled from the Fynbos, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Thicket and Savanna Biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

Figures 1–3. *Synema simoneae*: 1–2. Female dorsal view. 3. Immature male from Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Tanzania, Lesotho, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA AND LESOTHO

Eastern Cape: Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Prentjiesberg (-31.18, 28.28). **Gauteng:** Irene, Gem Village Field (-25.87, 28.22); Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Cathedral Peak (-28.94, 29.19); Highmoor (-29.30, 29.59); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, uMkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Loteni Nature Reserve (-29.47, 29.52); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Royal Natal National Park (-28.73, 28.92); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Tuinplaas (-24.90, 28.73). **Western Cape:** Du Toitskloof (-33.724, 19.151). **Lesotho:** Mohale Dam Islands (-29.42, 28.08).

Figures 4–8. *Synema simoneae* female: 4–5. Line drawing of abdomen and epigyne after Lessert (1919). 6. Epigyne. 7–8. Female on vegetation at Irene. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

CONSERVATION

An African endemic known from Tanzania in the north and South Africa and Lesotho in the south. This species is possibly under-collected and suspected to occur in more localities.

Due to its wide range, it is listed as Least Concern. In South Africa the species is protected in the Mountain Zebra National Park, Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989), uMkuze Game Reserve, Loteni Nature Reserve, Royal Natal National Park, Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006), and Tembe Elephant Park.

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